

Master thesis on Sound and Music Computing
Universitat Pompeu Fabra

Understanding Internal Semantics of Deep Learning Models for Electronic Music

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Abstract

Since deep learning showed outstanding performance in the computer vision field, Music Information Retrieval (MIR) researchers also started to adopt these successful models in their research area. Unfortunately, a number of publications are still simply applying deep learning algorithms to any new problems or dataset without understanding their models. For sophisticated model design process, interpreting the architecture and the mechanism of hidden layers became more important, and it resulted in multiple publications to propose methods for investigating learnt information in hidden layers: visualization, auralization, and playlist generation. However, due to the fact that proposed methods are very time-consuming processes, hidden layers still remain a black-box. In this paper, I propose two ideas to investigate hidden layers more efficiently, which are *ranking tags* and *deriving filter importances*. With conventional approaches and proposed methods, I investigate latent semantics learnt in hidden layers of deep learning models, particularly Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs). A prototype experiment was processed with Ballroom dataset and the main experiment was done with Beatport dataset which consists of 15k electronic music. The experimental result reports latent semantics of learnt kernels from pre-trained CNNs for the electronic music genre classification, which was not mainly explored in a deep learning research.

Keywords: Convolutional Neural Networks; Hidden Layers; Music Semantic

Chapter 1

Introduction

Through the last three decades, multiple Music Information Retrieval (MIR) researchers tried to *extract* meaningful features from music, *index* music using extracted features, and develop *search* and *retrieval* systems with signal processing approaches [1][2]. Whereupon, state of the art algorithms for feature extraction tasks have their accuracy around 80%. Since there is 20% of room for the betterment, MIR researchers have started to write about the semantic gap [3], which is the mismatch between human perceptual semantics and audio signal based music features. Wiggins [4] argued two reasons for this 20% room, which is referred as a semantic gap or a glass ceiling. One is that the applied audio signal processing technique was not good enough, and another is that the information is not in the audio signal. So far state of the art algorithms cannot extract music semantics as a human does with audio, which means still there is a room for the improvement only with audio signal. To this end, in this paper, I mainly discuss with the semantic gap which results from the former reason, *the applied technique was not good enough*, and pursue methods that can bridge the gap.

MIR research traditionally relied on two-stage approaches: feature extraction from the audio and using them for the regression or the classification [5]. These content-based approaches were designed under careful consideration of utilizing their domain knowledge to extract music information from the audio. However, Humphrey et al.

[6] mentioned three drawbacks of those approaches: hand-crafted feature design is unsustainable, shallow processing structures cannot characterize latent complexity of the data, short-time analysis cannot describe high-level information of music. They discussed potential of deep learning in MIR to leverage latent information from music audio.

After the great success of deep learning in the computer vision field [7], these methods have been explored in many other research areas including MIR [8][9][5][10][11]. However, since deep learning algorithms learn information from the data automatically, they are less intuitive and less understandable. Unfortunately, this led to a large number of research blindly applying deep learning to any new problem or dataset. The main drawback of approaching deep learning in such a way is that it is not clear how to navigate through the network parameters space. It is hard to discover the adequate combination of parameters for a particular task, what leads to architectures being difficult to interpret [12]. Furthermore, since music domain knowledge does not influence current deep learning research, this leads to a gap between many current and previous MIR studies. Implicitly, some research renounces to the knowledge acquired throughout the years designing features.

Recent publications [13][14] reported that music audio features and music semantics have been learnt in hidden layers of classification models using Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) algorithms. To this end, researchers proposed methods for demystifying hidden layers of CNNs: visualization [15], auralization [16], and playlist generation [13]. However, due to the huge time consumption of the analysis, hidden layers of CNNs still remain a black-box.

This paper aims to investigate hidden layers of CNNs in purpose of interpreting architectures and demystifying latent music semantics. To this end, I propose novel ideas for analyzing hidden layers efficiently and report experiments using two datasets which are Ballroom dataset and Beatport dataset. With two experiments, I unveil learnt latent semantics of ballroom dance music and electronic music. In Chapter 2, I explain recent development of CNNs and conventional methodologies for exploring hidden layers in detail. Chapter 3 introduces prototype experiment us-

ing proposing methods applied to the Ballroom dataset. Chapter 4 reports results for the main experiment using same methodologies applied to a bigger dataset. And the Chapter 5 includes conclusion and future work.

Chapter 2

State of the Art

2.1 Convolutional Neural Network

Deep Learning is an area of machine learning research whose models consisting of multiple layers. Deep learning models learn feature representation at higher and more abstract layers [17]. After the great success of deep learning, especially using Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), in the computer vision field [7], these methods have been actively explored in many other research areas including MIR.

A CNN was proposed by LeCun et al. [18] and it could reduce the training time, the network size, and the number of parameters successfully, which were considered as weaknesses of the conventional multi-layered neural networks. A CNN consists of convolutional layers and subsampling layers (Figure 1). In convolutional layers, it computes 2D-convolution of the part of input image and the trained filter weights. Then the subsampling layer will subsample representative values, such as max or mean, from the convoluted results. These local connectivities operate like a receptive field of the human neuron and provide robustness against transformations of the image.

The rapid growth of computing power and data accessibility induced active research in deep learning field. Especially, the AlexNet [7] showed outstanding results in the ImageNet Large Scale Visual Recognition Challenge 2012 (ILSVRC 2012) by using

Figure 1: A convolutional layer and a subsampling layer of the CNN.

CNNs with Graphics Processing Units (GPUs), and it has accelerated consecutive researchers to go deeper with CNNs and GPUs. Indeed, compare to the fact that AlexNet [7] consists of only 8 layers, ResNet [19] won the first place on the ILSVRC 2015 classification task with 152 layers.

2.1.1 LeNet

The LeNet [18] consists of convolutional layers, subsampling layers, and fully-connected layers. In the convolutional layers, the model acquires local connectivities with 2D convolution and it results in smaller feature maps because the model does not use the zero padding. These feature maps include information regarding prominent characteristics of the input image such as lines, curves, or corners. Since those features can appear at various locations of the image, the model facilitates the feature detection at any location with the *weight sharing* technique. From the convoluted feature maps, the subsampling layers picks only striking values. It can be described as an undersampling, and some location information is eliminated. While the model loses the exact position of the feature, it detects the presence of the feature. Subsampled feature maps are flattened and connected to the fully-connected layers.

2.1.2 AlexNet

The AlexNet [7] is a name of a CNN model which won the ILSVRC 2012. It consists of 5 convolutional layers and 3 fully-connected layers. The AlexNet reported remarkable result with using GPUs. Not only the GPU usage, they put more considerations for their model design. Most of the biologically inspired neural network models used the sigmoid or the hyperbolic tangent as their nonlinear activation function. However, the sigmoid or hyperbolic tangent function make the learning slower when the size of network becomes bigger. The AlexNet used the Rectified Linear Unit (ReLU) as its nonlinear activation function in order to make the learning faster. The ReLU only passes positive values as shown in below.

$$f_{ReLU}(x) = \max(0, x) \quad (2.1)$$

They reported that the ReLU reached a 25% training error rate on CIFAR-10 dataset six times faster than a same network using hyperbolic tangent units.

Authors of the AlexNet also used the dropout [20] to prevent the model from overfitting. When a large network is trained with a small dataset, the network performs worse on test set although its training accuracy is high. Not only conducting data augmentation, by omitting hidden units of the network randomly, they successfully prevented overfitting on the training data.

2.1.3 VGGNET

The VGG Net [21] was introduced in ILSVRC 2014. They mainly discussed the effect of the CNN depth on its accuracy. If the kernel sizes become smaller, the network becomes deeper to represent bigger kernel size. They proved that the deeper structure with smaller kernels is beneficial for larger datasets. Not only reducing the number of parameters, it improves the accuracy.

Figure 2: A CNN model proposed by Han et al. [11] for music instrument recognition.

2.2 CNNs in music

Although the CNN was designed for the image processing tasks, a number of researchers applied this successful model to the spectrogram, which is a time-frequency visual representation of the audio. Since seeing a spectrogram can give audio related information, this approach demonstrated good performance in a variety of MIR tasks. Lee et al. [8] considered to be the first work doing feature learning with spectrograms-based CNNs. They explored what their models were learning by visually inspecting first layer filters.

Schluter et al. [9] presented an improved onset detection model with a CNN. Dieleman et al. [5] and Choi et al. [10] proposed automatic tagging systems using CNNs. Pons et al. [12] introduced a genre classification CNN model with a noble filter design strategy considering the domain knowledge (This design strategy will be discussed more concretely in the next subsection 2.3). Han et al. [11] demonstrated a CNN model for musical instrument recognition by following an AlexNet [7] and VGGNet [21] structure. As shown in Figure 2, the model consists of multiple convolutional layers followed by subsampling layers and a fully-connected layer.

2.3 Filter design

Most CNNs use small rectangular filters, which achieved remarkable results in the computer vision field. However, small rectangular filters cannot model enough context for capturing temporal patterns in their first layer – it would require to combine several filters, what implies: learning filters that are difficult to interpret alone, and paying the cost of using more filters. To avoid these issues, Pons et al. [22] proposed a novel CNN architecture where filters can learn temporal patterns, see Figure 3. Proposed filters have different $1\text{-by-}n^1$ shapes instead of the conventional $m\text{-by-}n$ rectangular shape. While the model loses the timbral information, these $1\text{-by-}n$ filters facilitate learning temporal patterns at different time-scales. Two complementary architectures were defined [22]:

- ***O-net*** is designed to efficiently model *onsets* with different short convolutional filters of $1\text{-by-}n$, where: $n \in [6, 11, 16, 21, 26, 31, 36, 41]$. *O-net* consists on 5 filters for each different filter length n . In total, there are 40 filters in the same (first) layer.
- ***P-net*** is designed to efficiently model *temporal patterns* (*ie.* rhythm or tempo) by using different longer convolutional filters of $1\text{-by-}n$ with $n \in 46 + 5 \cdot f$ where $f \in \mathbb{Z} \mid 0 \leq f \leq 34$ stands for the filter number. The *P-net* consists on 35 filters of different length in the first layer ranging from $46 \leq n \leq 216$.

Figure 3: $1\text{-by-}n$ shaped filters.

¹Used model is a spectrogram-based CNN model, with the input being of dimensions $M\text{-by-}N$ and the filter dimensions of $m\text{-by-}n$. M and m standing for the number of frequency bins and N and n for the number of time frames.

Input of the CNN model is a mel-spectrogram which consists of 40 mel frequency bands. The Short Time Fourier Transform (STFT) was computed with 2048 point Fast Fourier Transform with 50% hop size at 44.1kHz. It means, the longest *O-net* filter ($n = 41$) can include 0.95 seconds which is approximately an inter-beat interval of 60 bpm. The longest *P-net* filter ($n = 216$) can include 5.02 seconds that is a length longer than four beats.

Both architectures are combined in parallel and, as a result, the resulting model is shallow: a single layer with many different filters. On top of this parallel combination of CNNs a max-pool layer of 4-by- N^2 is utilized – note that the resulting feature map of the max-pool layer can be interpreted as a 10 bands summary[22]. Finally an 8-way softmax is set as output, where each unit corresponds to a Ballroom class. As seen, here described architecture is highly interpretable because domain knowledge informed the architecture design.

The audio is fed to the CNN through chunks of fixed-length mel spectrograms, $N = 250$ frames wide. 40 bands mel-spectrograms derived from a STFT-spectrogram were used. Phases are discarded. A logarithmic compression is applied to the input spectrograms element-wise and the resulting spectrograms are normalized (zero mean and unit variance). ReLUs are set as nonlinearities. They reported that the best accuracy result was achieved with the following model: $8x$ *O-net* + $8x$ *P-net* – 92.27% accuracy. $2x$ *O-net* + $2x$ *P-net* is smaller but still performs reasonably (91.27% accuracy).

2.4 Exploring Hidden layers

This section discusses conventional methods for investigating learnt features or quantifying the interpretability of latent representations. With *visualization* [15], *auralization* [16], *playlist generation* [13], and *network dissection* [23] methods, previous researches pursued to gain intuition about the trained network.

² N' and M' denote, in general, the dimensions of any feature map. Although the filter map dimensions will be different depending on the filter size, they refer to their dimensions by the same name: N' and M' .

Figure 4: The max pooling and the unpooling using switches.

2.4.1 Visualization

The ZF Net [15] outperformed Alex Net [7] on the ImageNet classification benchmark by introducing a novel visualization technique. To prevent from designing models with less scientific approaches, *trial-and-error*, authors investigated internal behaviors of the CNN by visualizing learnt information. Their visualization technique used a multi-layered Deconvolutional Network [24].

Standard fully supervised CNN models, such as the LeNet [18] and the AlexNet [7] consist of (i) convolutional layers; (ii) non-linearity activation functions; (iii) subsampling layers. Visualizing learnt features (activation maps) to the pixel space is only available for the first convolutional layer. This interpretability of the first layer was the motivation of the filter design strategy of Pons et al. [12][25].

Zeiler et al. introduced a method to follow all the steps backward, *unpooling*, *ReLU*, and *deconvolution*, for enabling projections of the deeper layer activation maps on the input pixel space. Although we lose negative information with ReLU nonlinearity, prominent values are preserved. And it is possible to project the feature activation to the previous feature map space using the deconvolution. However, in the step of unpooling, there is no information regarding positions of the maximum values.

Zeiler et al. proposed a novel method, *switch*, to solve this problem. As shown in Figure 4, authors stored positions of maximum values when they feed forward the input data. These switches are used for restoring max-pooled data to the previous feature map again. By this mean, authors demonstrated the visualization of the network successfully.

Simonyan et al. introduced more simple way of visualization called *saliency maps* [26]. It just simply obtains by rearranging the elements of the derivative vector w , which is found by back-propagation.

The Keras-vis [27] is a high-level toolkit for visualizing and debugging trained Keras models. It is available for visualizing the activations maximization, saliency maps, and class activation maps. In this thesis, I used this Keras implementation for analyzing hidden layers of the trained network.

2.4.2 Auralization

Most of CNN-based models for music analysis use spectrograms or mel-spectrograms. This regards *seeing* a spectrogram or a mel-spectrogram as *listening* to the audio. However, different from images, it is sometimes difficult to understand what was learnt in the feature map only with seeing those time-frequency representations. To this end, Choi et al. [16] proposed a novel method to get better intuitions of learnt information by listening to the audio, called *auralization*. Authors stored the phase of the original STFT. And they used the phase information with the deconvolved spectrogram to reconstruct the time-domain audio signal. By seeing the spectrogram with listening to the audio, they could have better intuitions for analyzing learnt features.

2.4.3 Playlist generation

Oord and Dieleman tackled a problem of predicting listener preferences by deriving latent representations, which were obtained from a collaborative filtering model, of the audio [28]. And Dieleman expanded this research during his internship at

Spotify with larger dataset. He explained the approach and preliminary results on his technical blog [13]. In the posting, he proposed a playlist generation method for listening to the audio clips that activate a certain kernel. Similar to the Auralization method, he tried to get better intuitions by *listening*.

Dieleman generated playlists with three different ways: (i) maximal activation, (ii) average activation, and (iii) activation at the top most layer. First, he made a playlist with songs that maximally activate a certain filter. By this mean, he reported several filters from the first layer that learnt vibrato singing, ambient, vocal thirds, or bass drums. For the second method, he computed the average activation of each feature across time. The author reported that it was more useful for detecting harmonic patterns. And third methodology was a playlist generation at the top most layer, which is not a convolutional layer. It is impossible to visualize or auralize learnt information since it is a unit of the fully-connected layer. However, it turned out to be very selective for specific subgenres. Demonstrated playlists include Gospel, Chinese pop, Deep house, and Chiptune.

2.4.4 Network dissection

The importance of interpretability of large networks resulted in multiple publications for analyzing latent representations. Bau et al. [23] discussed how to quantify and detect factors of disentangled representations in their recent publication. The proposed network dissection method includes: (i) identify human-labeled visual concepts, (ii) gather hidden variables' response to known concepts, and (iii) quantify alignment of hidden variable-concept pairs.

Authors introduced the Broadly and Densely Labeled Dataset (Broden) for their experiment. The Broden is a pixel-wise annotated dataset in six types of label: scene, object, part, material, texture, and color. With this pixel-wise annotated dataset, the Broden, they proposed a novel way to score unit interpretability. From a given image \mathbf{x} , $A_k(\mathbf{x})$ denotes an activation map of unit k in convolutional layers. For each unit k , T_k is computed which is a threshold for the top quantile level. To compare with an annotated mask L_c , the activation map $A_k(\mathbf{x})$ is projected

to the input image space using bilinear interpolation ($S_k(\mathbf{x})$). Then the $S_k(\mathbf{x})$ is thresholded by the top quantile level T_k : $M_k(\mathbf{x}) \equiv S_k(\mathbf{x}) \geq T_k$. The score of unit k for the concept (label type) c is calculated as an intersection over union score shown in below.

$$IoU_{k,c} = \frac{\sum |M_k(\mathbf{x}) \cap L_c(\mathbf{x})|}{\sum |M_k(\mathbf{x}) \cup L_c(\mathbf{x})|} \quad (2.2)$$

However, since two datasets in my thesis, the Ballroom dataset and the Beatport dataset, are not pixel-wisely annotated, this network dissection methodology will not be used for the analysis. Instead, I am going to discuss this method for the future work.

2.4.5 Limitations

These previous approaches, Visualization using deconvolution, Auralization with phase information, and the Playlist generation, give better intuitions for analyzing learnt features in the hidden layers of CNNs. However, these methods have a main drawback, time consumption. Especially, music is a time sequence. It takes more time for listening compare to seeing an image. Through the next chapter, I propose more efficient way of analyzing latent learnt features of CNNs for music.

Chapter 3

Prototype

This chapter describes prototype experiment with a pre-trained model [25] using the Ballroom dataset [29]. First of all, I focus on inspecting the CNN layer – where I expect to find temporal patterns: rhythm and tempo. Secondly, I explore the output connections – that connect the max-pool layer (where information from 10 sub-bands is present[22]) and the softmax layer (where the 8 output classes are represented). Latter inspection will provide information of which filters and bands are important for predicting the Ballroom genres with the studied model.

3.1 Ballroom dataset

The Ballroom dataset was created for evaluating rhythmic descriptors [29] and it consists of 698 ballroom dance music excerpts, each ≈ 30 seconds long. Audio excerpts are divided into 8 genre classes¹ and are also annotated by tempo (BPM). It has been found that tempo is the most significant predictor of the genres in the Ballroom dataset [29] – this being one of the major criticisms against this dataset, since tempo acts as a confounding factor for evaluating rhythmic descriptors. Figure 5 shows the tempo distributions of each genre in the dataset. One can observe that music excerpts of the same genre are mostly concentrated around a certain BPM range. Therefore, I consider rhythm and tempo to be the most relevant audio

¹ChaChaCha, Jive, Quickstep, Rumba, Samba, Tango, VienneseWaltz and Waltz.

Figure 5: Ballroom dataset tempo distributions per genre.

features for this dataset.

Previous research used this dataset for benchmarking. The state-of-the-art is held by Marchand et al. [30], with 96% accuracy. This method is based on a scale and shift invariant time/frequency representation that uses auditory statistics. But it requires manual annotation for the first onset. The best performing deep learning method was proposed by Pons et al. [22], achieving 92.27% accuracy – and I chose to dissect these deep learning models for their competitive results and interpretability. Note that it seems reasonable that deep learning methods perform worse than traditional MIR methods in this scenario where only small amounts of data are available for training.

Used model design was motivated by the above-mentioned main characteristics of the dataset: the relevance of temporal features (tempo and rhythm) and the small size of it. Since deep learning methods are data driven approaches, I expect tempo and rhythm to be expressed in the observed model because Ballroom classes are

highly correlated with those. Moreover a small network is required for such a small dataset, which facilitates the exploration process.

3.2 Observations

3.2.1 Tag activations: tempo

Method 1: To mitigate a possible bias due to data unbalance, 6528 spectrogram chunks (816 chunks \times 8 genres) were randomly chosen as input data – where 816 is a number of chunks in the smallest genre class (Jive). Selected input chunks were processed by a CNN layer, and maximum values measured in the resulting feature maps were ranked for each filter. I used the Average Precision (AveP) to consider the order of the ranked sequence in the observations. Considering ranked chunks, I computed the AveP@100 considering tempo annotations in order to study the sensitivity of filters to a given tempo.

I also compared filters’ tempo sensitivity with learnt filters’ periodicity by visualizing the autocorrelation² of each filter below the AveP plot – x-axis of autocorrelation plots are converted to BPMs, so that axis are comparable. If the highest peaks in the AveP and the autocorrelation graphics are aligned within $\pm 4\%$ error (which is the standard error for the MIREX Audio Tempo Estimation task), I considered that the filter is modeling the tempo. I only dealt with the 70 $2x$ *P-net* filters for this analysis because it was not accurate to estimate periodicity of $2x$ *O-net* filters due to their short lengths. Also, *P-net* architecture is known to be more decisive for the classification [22].

Observation 1. The highest AveP and autocorrelation peaks are aligned for 21 out of 70 filters – i.e. as in Figure 6 (a). Meaning that these filters have learnt temporal patterns related to a specific tempo.

Observation 2. If octave errors are admitted (which is a phenomenon that can be also observed in human perceptions), 32 out of 70 filters turned out to be within the

²To get a better BPM resolution, I interpolated the filter by 10 times.

Figure 6: Average precisions of BPM tags and autocorrelations of learnt filters

$\pm 4\%$ error, meaning that these have learnt tempo as well – i.e. see Figure 6 (b).

Observation 3. Still, 38 out of 70 filters remain unexplained – denoting that for those filters AveP and autocorrelation peaks are not sufficiently aligned. However, 19 filters showed periodicity. They have autocorrelation peaks at their highest AveP BPM indices – i.e. as in Figure 6 (c).

Observation 4. Remaining 19 filters do not show strong peaks in the autocorrelation graphic, denoting that these filters did not learn tempo – i.e. see Figure 6 (d).

3.2.2 Tag activations: genre

Method 2: The same 6528 spectrogram chunks ($816 \text{ chunks} \times 8 \text{ genres}$) were ranked following the same procedure as in *Method 1*. However, in this case I considered both *O-net* and *P-net* architectures. Considering ranked chunks, I computed

the AveP@100 considering genre annotations in order to study the sensitivity of filters to a given genre. For seeing if a filter is specialized in a Ballroom genre, I set an AveP@100 score-threshold to 0.75 – meaning that this filter is mostly activated for a genre.

Observation 5. The following filters have their AveP above 0.75: 13 ChaChaCha filters (9 from *P-net*, 4 from *O-net*), 11 Jive filters (7 from *P-net*, 4 from *O-net*), 7 Quickstep (*P-net*) filters, 8 Samba (*P-net*) filters, 4 Tango (*P-net*) filters, and 1 VienneseWaltz (*P-net*) filter. Therefore, *P-net* filters (capable to learn temporal patterns) show consistent higher activations than *O-net* filters for a specific genre.

Observation 6. From the filters selected in *Observation 5*, the following have learnt tempo³:

- 8 out of 13 for ChaChaCha learnt tempo around 124 BPM.
- 9 out of 11 for Jive learnt tempo around 172 BPM.
- 5 out of 7 for Quickstep learnt tempo around 204 BPM.
- 7 out of 8 for Samba learnt tempo around 100 BPM.
- 2 out of 4 for Tango learnt tempo around 128 BPM.
- 0 out of 1 for VienneseWaltz learnt tempo.

Observation 7. The tempos learnt by the selected filters are in concordance with the median value (or its octave error) of the annotated tempos of the genre, see Figure 5.

Observation 8. There are no filters with high AveP for Rumba and Waltz, denoting that this method is not useful for identifying relevant filters for these genres. Possibly because *Method 2* is biased towards chunks having more energy – since activations are influenced by input energy.

³In *Method 1*, filters have learnt tempo if: *i*) highest peaks in the AveP and the autocorrelation graphics are aligned within $\pm 4\%$ error, or *ii*) such alignment occurs at the double or the half of the AveP peak indices.

3.2.3 Visualizations

Method 3: All input spectrograms are divided into chunks and ranked (as in *Method 1*) for each filter. This ranking is visually inspected in descending order. Rhythmic patterns are identified by observing which temporal patterns typically activate a CNN filter, and by also listening to highly ranked chunks for identifying commonalities.

Observation 9. ChaChaCha, Jive, Quickstep, Samba, Tango, and VienneseWaltz are activated by their related filters at lower frequency bands, and I can observe evident beat patterns by visualizing, i.e., Figure 7 spectrograms. These learnt rhythmic patterns are consistent along chunks – and are steady and tempo variant.

Figure 7: Spectrograms and filters aligned at the maximum activations.

Observation 10. Waltz, the only genre which does not have kick drums in the dataset, was activated at higher bands by its related filters. Waltz related filters often detect the existence of repetitive arpeggios – see Figure 7 (h) – although this

characteristic is not present throughout all Walz chunks. Additionally, note that these arpeggios consist of different notes (expressed in different frequency bins) and therefore, *1-by-n* filters cannot capture it. However, observe that note onsets affect neighboring frequency bins and these arpeggios can be modeled by *1-by-n* filters.

Observation 11. It was difficult to identify which rhythmic patterns were relevant for detecting Rumba, having the worst classification accuracy (85%). Since Rumba has the most widely spread BPM range, and the model learns tempo variant filters, none of filters learnt significant patterns of Rumba. *Method 4* will help understanding which patterns are relevant for discriminating Rumba.

3.2.4 Filter importances

I could not justify the role of each filter only with their activations at the convolutional layer, because: *(i)* weights play a role towards the output, and *(ii)* the activation values, carrying energy information, are not comparable as certain genres have higher energy than others – which can cause high activations although the filter is not critical for the decision.

Method 4: I aim to discover the important filters for each genre. For checking the precise filter mechanism, only correctly classified chunks for each genre were input. Selected audio chunks for each genre were passed through the convolutional layer and the max-pool layer. Derived 10 values from each filter’s max-pool layer were multiplied by learnt weights in the fully-connected dense layer. I could get 8 output values (right before the softmax) for each filter – I visualized them in a plot with 8 box-plots summarizing the obtained values for every chunk. I repeated this for every filter and every input genre. The median level depicted in each box-plot can be interpreted as the *regular filter contribution* to an output-unit given an input genre.

Then, I sum the output values of previous 150 filters for each output-unit and I add its corresponding bias term – what results in mapping 1200 plots (150 filters×8 input genres) into 8 plots (8 input genres), see 8. The median level depicted in each

Figure 8: Boxplots of the genre decision boundaries.

box-plot can be interpreted as the *genre decision boundary* for each output unit given a fixed input genre.

Finally I designed a relative measure for identifying important filters as the *ratio* between each *regular filter contribution* and its *genre decision boundary* – I arbitrarily define filters with a *ratio* $\geq 5\%$ as important filters.

Observation 12. Cha Cha Cha shows the highest *genre decision boundary* around 12 – 8 (top-left) –, since it has steady and obvious kick patterns around BPM 124 with high energy – see 7 (a), as well.

Observation 13. The following filters are selected as important: 10 ChaChaCha filters (7 from *P-net* and 3 from *O-net*), 10 Jive filters (8 from *P-net* and 2 from *O-net*), 12 Quickstep filters (11 from *P-net* and 1 from *O-net*), 9 Rumba filters (1 from *P-net* and 8 from *O-net*), 10 Samba filters (9 from *P-net* and 1 from *O-net*), 12 Tango filters (11 from *P-net* and 1 from *O-net*), 10 VienneseWaltz filters (10 from

P-net and 0 from *O-net*) and 18 Waltz filters (15 from *P-net* and 3 from *O-net*). Therefore, *P-net* filters (capable to learn temporal patterns) are more important than *O-net* filters for all genres except for Rumba.

Observation 14. From the selected important filters in *Observation 13*, the following have learnt tempo⁹:

- 10 out of 10 for ChaChaCha learnt tempo around 124 BPM.
- 7 out of 10 for Jive learnt tempo around 172 BPM.
- 8 out of 12 for Quickstep learnt tempo around 102 and 204 BPM.
- 1 out of 9 for Rumba learnt tempo around 204 BPM.
- 9 out of 10 for Samba learnt tempo around 100 BPM.
- 11 out of 12 for Tango learnt tempo around 128 BPM.
- 7 out of 10 for VienneseWaltz learnt tempo around 180 BPM.
- 6 out of 18 for Waltz learnt tempo around 172 BPM.

Observation 15. The tempos learnt by the selected filters are in concordance with the median value (or its octave error) of the annotated tempos of the genre, see Figure 5.

Observation 16. Rumba is the only genre with more *O-net* than *P-net* important filters. These *O-net* filters react to a single onset of a clave- or bongo-like percussive sound, i.e., as in Figure 7 (d). I speculated that the network learnt an amplitude envelope of a clave- or bongo-like sound instead of learning tempo related patterns because Rumba class has a wide range of different BPMs – see Figure 5. Indeed, activations of higher bands in Rumba contributes more to the decision boundary than other genres.

Observation 17. Viennese Waltz and Waltz have negative correlation with other genres in this network – see that in Figure 8 their output units have negative activa-

tions for other genres. Interestingly these other genres have 4/4 time signature⁴, as opposed to VienneseWaltz or Waltz which are in 3/4 time signature. But for Jive, this phenomenon was not as strong as other genres since Jive shares the BPM range with Viennese Waltz and also is in octave relation with Waltz BPMs.

⁴Cha Cha Cha, Jive, Quickstep, Rumba, Samba and Tango.

Chapter 4

Experiment

4.1 Beatport dataset

Beatport [31] is one of the biggest online music store established in 2004, specifically electronic music oriented. Not only the basic metadata, they also provide tag data for users to discover and explore new album releases. Since I proposed an analysis method using tag activations, especially using AveP, the abundance of tag data was fascinating for me to conduct the experiment. From 26 genres, I have chosen 5 most popular genres which are Deep House, Electro House, House, Tech House, and Techno. I collected 15,000 pre-listen audio (2 minute-long, 3,000 clips \times 5 genres). Each audio clip includes a tempo tag (BPM), mood tags, venue tags, and set-time tags. Mood tags describe mood of the audio clip. There are 96 different moods for mood tags. Venue tags describe to which venue this track is suitable since Beatport is an electronic music oriented online music store for the dance floor i.e. Club (large), Warehouse, Poolside, etc. Set-time tags suggest appropriate set-time for the given audio track i.e. Warmup, Peak hour, Afterhours, Sunrise, etc.

Layer (type)	Output Shape	Param #
input_1 (InputLayer)	(None, 257, 174, 1)	0
conv2d_1 (Conv2D)	(None, 257, 174, 64)	640
activation_1 (Activation)	(None, 257, 174, 64)	0
max_pooling2d_1 (MaxPooling2D)	(None, 128, 87, 64)	0
dropout_1 (Dropout)	(None, 128, 87, 64)	0
conv2d_2 (Conv2D)	(None, 128, 87, 64)	36928
activation_2 (Activation)	(None, 128, 87, 64)	0
max_pooling2d_2 (MaxPooling2D)	(None, 64, 43, 64)	0
dropout_2 (Dropout)	(None, 64, 43, 64)	0
conv2d_3 (Conv2D)	(None, 64, 43, 64)	36928
activation_3 (Activation)	(None, 64, 43, 64)	0
max_pooling2d_3 (MaxPooling2D)	(None, 32, 21, 64)	0
dropout_3 (Dropout)	(None, 32, 21, 64)	0
conv2d_4 (Conv2D)	(None, 32, 21, 64)	36928
activation_4 (Activation)	(None, 32, 21, 64)	0
max_pooling2d_4 (MaxPooling2D)	(None, 16, 10, 64)	0
dropout_4 (Dropout)	(None, 16, 10, 64)	0
conv2d_5 (Conv2D)	(None, 16, 10, 64)	36928
activation_5 (Activation)	(None, 16, 10, 64)	0
max_pooling2d_5 (MaxPooling2D)	(None, 8, 5, 64)	0
flatten_1 (Flatten)	(None, 2560)	0
dropout_5 (Dropout)	(None, 2560)	0
FC1 (Dense)	(None, 1024)	2622464
dropout_6 (Dropout)	(None, 1024)	0
FC2 (Dense)	(None, 1024)	1049600
dropout_7 (Dropout)	(None, 1024)	0
prediction_raw (Dense)	(None, 5)	5125
activation_6 (Activation)	(None, 5)	0
Total params: 3,825,541		
Trainable params: 3,825,541		
Non-trainable params: 0		

Figure 9: Summary of the used model.

Figure 10: Confusion matrix of the trained model. Order of the class is Electro House, House, Tech House, Deep House, and Techno respectively.

4.2 Model design

Different from the Ballroom dataset, which was used in the prototype experiment, tempo (BPM) is not the only criteria for the genre classification. All of five genres share their BPM range around 120 to 130 BPM. For the better classification accuracy, I used conventional rectangular filters instead of *1-by-n* shaped filters. A model used in this experiment is a conventional AlexNet or VGG Net style model that proposed in a publication of Choi et al. [14].

From 15,000 songs (3,000 songs \times 5 genres), 10 chunks of 4 seconds were extracted from each song with an 11.6-second interval. 135,000 chunks were used for the training, and 15,000 chunks were used for the validation. Each chunk was down-sampled at 11,025 *Hz*, and STFT was computed with 512-point FFT (50% hop size).

The model consists of five convolutional layers and two fully connected layers. ReLU, Max pooling layers, and Dropout were followed after each convolutional layer. For

all convolutional layers, 3×3 shaped kernels were used with zero-padding which mean that the size of feature map before and after the convolution are same. Max pooling layers have 2×2 receptive field with 2×2 strides which means that the width and height of the feature map after the max pooling will be a half of the previous feature map. The number of parameters, sizes of feature maps, and the summary of the model are described in the Figure 9. I used Adam for the optimizer, categorical cross-entropy for calculating loss. I run the experiment for 100 epochs. For the faster experiment, all of the procedures including training and analysis used GPUs.

A training accuracy of the model was 53.61% and a validation accuracy was 48.42%. As shown in Figure 10, House (class 1) showed the worst classification accuracy due to the fact that House can also be a higher hierarchy of all of other House music. Before the experiment, I expected confusions between Deep House (class 3) and Tech House (class 2) because it is difficult to even for human in some cases and indeed there were high confusion rates. 743 Electro House were classified as Techno (class 4) although they have different musical characteristics except for the BPM. Reasons for the confusion and learnt information will be discussed in upcoming sections using *Visualization*, *Tag activation*, and *Filter importance* methods.

4.3 Important filters

Compare to the previous shallow network used in the prototype experiment, the current model has a huge number of parameters and kernels in its hidden layers (Figure 9). It takes extremely long time to explore every single learnt feature in the hidden layers. For the efficient analysis, I proposed the measurement of the filter importance by feed forwarding activation maps toward the output layer, but just before the Softmax. In this section, I introduce a concrete procedure of deriving filter importances.

I used 15,000 validation set for this procedure. For the first step, I chose 1,000 sample clips ($200 \text{ clips} \times 5 \text{ genres}$) that classify each genre with high confidence

Figure 11: Overall filter importances of each layer and genre.

(high values at the output layer). The reason for this sampling step is to check the exact mechanism of the network and 1,000 was an arbitrary value.

Calculating filter importance of the fifth layer is same as the method proposed in the previous chapter. By feed-forwarding an activation of a target filter, with setting rest of filter activations as zeros, the contribution of the target filter can be derived easily. However, since current model consists of multiple layers, I had to derive *switches* of ReLU and the max-pooling [15] in advance for lower layer (1 to 4) filters. If the feed-forwarding step is conducted without deriving switches, the result will be different from the original mechanism of the network because it will

follow the new positions of ReLU and the max-pooling. From a given spectrogram X , filter importance of the l -th layer and the k -th filter $I_{l,k}$ can be derived as:

$$I_{l,k}(X) = \frac{F_{l,k}(X) - bias}{D_{l,k}(X) - bias} \quad (4.1)$$

where $F_{l,k}(X)$ is a feed-forwarded value of the l -th layer and the k -th filter, $D_{l,k}(X)$ is the decision boundary before the softmax layer. Although $I_{l,k}$, $F_{l,k}(X)$, and $D_{l,k}(X)$ are *1-by-5* arrays since this model has five classes, I only chose an index of the target genre to check the importance for a certain genre.

Every spectrogram have different importance values. To determine their overall importance, I simply added the inverse of their ranks. Filter importances of overall samples can be described as:

$$I_{l,k,overall} = \sum_X \frac{1}{Rank_{l,k}(X)} \quad (4.2)$$

where $Rank_{l,k}(X)$ is the rank of the layer l , filter k . In this step, a rank of the filter can be only compared with filters in the same layer. To this end, the range of the rank is 1 to 64. Figure 11 shows the result $I_{l,k,overall}$ for the 1,000 given audio clips. Each row is a depth of the layer, and each column is a genre. The *x-axis* is the filter number and the *y-axis* is the overall importance. As the layer goes deeper, there are more filters with higher overall importance values. This means that there are more genre specific filters in the deeper layer.

4.4 Learnt features

This section reports the results of exploring highly activated filters (important filters) by *seeing* spectrograms and saliency maps, *listening* to the audio, and *checking* tag activations. Checking tag activations is a procedure of visualizing AveP@200 of tags that highly activates each filter as proposed in the previous chapter. I used mood tags, venue tags, set-time tags, and BPM tags.

Figure 12: Spectrograms and saliency maps of filters that learnt the *build-up* (upper) and the *compressed kick* (lower)

4.4.1 First and the second layers

In the first layer and the second layer, 3×3 kernels can capture horizontal information of 93 ms and 162 ms , vertical information of 86 Hz and 151 Hz respectively [14]. They mostly detect onsets as reported in the previous research [14]. But they also learnt very short-time timbre information. Figure 12 (upper) shows a spectrogram and a saliency map of a filter that learnt the noisy sound of the build-up which is a typical characteristic of dance tunes before their *drop*. This sound mainly appears in Electro house, Techno, and House.

Figure 12 (lower) shows a spectrogram and a saliency map of a filter that learnt extremely short onsets. As shown in the spectrogram, when a kick arises, other frequency bands show low energies. This means highly compressed kick sounds which is a main characteristic of the Electro house. Indeed, in the tag analysis, it showed dominant peaks at *Whompy* (AveP: 0.49) and *Thick* (AveP: 0.49) mood tags, a *Club (large)* (AveP: 0.44) venue tag, *Peakhours* (AveP: 0.49) and *Filler* (AveP: 0.47) set-time tags, a *Electro house* genre tag.

Figure 13: Mood tag activations of the 25th filter (left) and the 28th filter (right) at the fourth layer.

4.4.2 Third and the fourth layers

In the third layer and the fourth layer, 3×3 kernels can capture horizontal information of 302 *ms* and 580 *ms*, vertical information of 280 *Hz* and 538 *Hz* respectively. Since they have more time-frequency information than lower layers, kernels in these layers learnt more specific timbres. And these learnt timbres are highly correlated to mood tags. Due to the fact that deeper layers tend to learn more multi-modal information, it becomes more difficult to define learnt information only with seeing the spectrogram and a saliency map. However, with listening to the audio and checking tag activations, I could get better intuitions for learnt information.

The 25th filter of the third layer, learnt a specific Tech house timbre with its acid bass sound. It activates *Mechanical* (AveP: 0.5) and *Acid* (AveP: 0.45) mood tags as shown in Figure 13 (left), a *Club (medium)* venue (AveP: 0.31) tag, a *Tech house* (AveP: 0.52) genre tag. BPM tags and set-time tags were not dominant for certain tags. The 28th filter of the third layer, learnt a deep house related timbre. It activates *Groovy* (AveP: 0.54) and *Deep* (AveP: 0.42) mood tags as shown in Figure 13 (right), a *Warmup* (AveP: 0.43) set-time tag, a 118 BPM tag (AveP: 0.44), and a *Deep house* (AveP: 0.43) genre tag. Venue tags did not show any characteristic. The 7th filter of the fourth layer, learnt a typical timbre of Techno kick sounds. It activated *Dark* (AveP: 0.72), *Ravey* (AveP: 0.67), *Bangin* (AveP: 0.51) mood tags,

Figure 14: Mood tag activations (left) and the BPM tag activations (right) of the 19th filter at the fifth layer. It learnt multi-modal information.

a *Peakhour* (AveP: 0.6) set-time tag, and a *Techno* (AveP: 0.93) genre tag.

It is difficult to say that each filter learnt those activated tags exactly. However, it is acceptable to analyze that learnt features in each filter are highly correlated to the activated tags. For example, the 28th filter of the third layer learnt a Deep house related timbre. And it also activates a 118 BPM in its AveP@200. However, a filter in the third layer cannot learn the tempo since it can only contain 302 *ms* of time information. The reason for the activation in that the learnt timbre is highly correlated to the 118 BPM in the validation set. To assure that the activated tag was learnt in a certain filter, input data should be equally distributed for other tag classes. But it is extremely difficult to collect dataset in such a way and the real-world data are not distributed like that.

4.4.3 Fifth layers

3×3 kernels of the fifth layer can capture horizontal information of 1137 *ms*, vertical information of 1270 *Hz*. Choi et al. reported that filters of the fifth layer learn textures and harmo-rhythmic structures [14]. Filters of the fifth layers learnt multi-modal high-level features. And they are highly correlated to the tempo and genre specific.

The 17th filter of the fifth layer learnt Techno drums. It activates *Driving* (AveP:

0.5) and *Dark* (AveP: 0.42) mood tags, a *Peakhour* (AveP: 0.73) set-time tag, a 130 BPM tag (AveP: 0.42), and a *Techno* (AveP: 0.8) genre tag. At the BPM 130, the beat interval is approximately 0.46 seconds. Since filters of the fifth layer can include at least two beats, it could learn tempo related features. Because this filter also learnt a timbre of the Techno drum, it mostly activates Techno at 130 BPM. However, it is also an important filter for the Electro house because most of Electro house has 128 to 130 BPM.

The 19th filter of the fifth layer activates Deep house clips at 110 BPM. It activates *Moombah* (AveP: 0.65) and *Bangin* (AveP: 0.65) mood tags, a *warmup* (AveP: 0.43) set-time tag, a 110 BPM tag (AveP: 0.46), and a *Deep house* (AveP: 0.58) genre tag as shown in Figure 14. Similar to the 17th filter, it is highly correlated to a certain BPM, 110. Although it is correlated to the Deep house, it activates House at 110 BPM which has similar pattern to other Deep house clips that highly activate the filter. Filters in the fifth layer learnt tempo related features and also a timbre related information at the same time.

Chapter 5

Discussion

5.1 Discussion

By experimenting with two datasets, I proposed two methodologies of analyzing learnt features in the hidden layers of CNNs and reported the result of the analysis. In this section, I propose three future works to improve this research. In the deeper layer, the network learnt high-level features. However, in this research I only explored convolutional layers since it is impossible to visualize or auralize the activations of fully-connected layers. Dieleman reported that higher level features were learnt in the fully-connected layers using the playlist generation method[13]. Although it is less intuitive analysis without the visualization, if I use the filter importance method for the fully-connected layer, it would be more intuitive for the analysis. By replacing the output of the filter importance calculation as an activation at the fully-connected layer instead of the output layer, it is possible to derive contributions of each kernel toward the unit of the fully-connected layer. If lower-level information that learnt in the convolutional layers are clear enough, it would be easier to interpret learnt information in the fully-connected layer by explaining with combinations of the lower-level information.

Filter importance has to be experimented with different designs or datasets more. If learnt filters are important for the task, the genre classification in this research,

similar filters will be learnt in other models or datasets for the same task. To determine the filter importance, it has to be confirmed that those filters will be learnt again. And this experiment will give better intuitions for the efficient transfer learning model design. Even if it is a different task, some of the features that are important for the entire music knowledge will be learnt. For example, when someone who can play the piano learns to play the guitar, he or she will use his or her pre-trained musical knowledge for playing the guitar.

This research also provides better ideas for designing CNN models for music. Spectrograms have different meanings from other visual images. Horizontal and vertical axes are time and frequency domain respectively, and human perception of the frequency range is not linear. Conventional 3×3 kernels can be effective for the timbre analysis. However, for the higher layers, kernels have to be designed under consideration of human perception or musical structures. The experimented model only used 4 seconds clip for the efficiency. Models that can include the structure of music have to be considered for the better accuracy.

5.2 Conclusion

Through the research I proposed novel ideas for exploring learnt features in hidden layers of the Convolutional Neural Networks, which are *deriving filter importances* and *ranking with Average Precisions*. With proposed methods and conventional methods, I explored hidden layers of CNN models for the genre classification in two datasets. In the prototype experiment, I proved the usefulness of proposed methods using a shallow network structure which eases the interpretability. And I investigated latent semantics of electronic music with a deeper network structure. In the lower layer, filters learnt low-level information such as onsets and noisiness. As the layer goes deeper, the network tends to learn multi-modal and high-level features including tempo and timbre characteristics. This research provides better intuition for comprehending learning mechanisms of the CNN models and designing more efficient network structures. Obtained knowledge also can be used for building transfer learning models to improve the machine listening systems.

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